

**NEW PROOFS OF CERTAIN THETA FUNCTION IDENTITIES
VIA RAMANUJAN'S FUNCTION**

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Abstract

We present new proofs of two theta function identities equivalent to Ramanujan's modular equations of degree five by employing some identities involving Ramanujan's function $k(q)$ due to Cooper, Chern, and Tang.

1. Introduction

Throughout this paper, we define $(a; q)_\infty := \prod_{n=0}^{\infty} (1 - aq^n)$ for complex numbers a and q with $|q| < 1$ and

$$(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_m; q)_\infty := (a_1; q)_\infty (a_2; q)_\infty \cdots (a_m; q)_\infty.$$

Recall that Ramanujan's general theta function is defined by

$$f(a, b) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} a^{n(n+1)/2} b^{n(n-1)/2} = (-a, -b, ab; ab)_\infty$$

for all complex numbers a and b with $|ab| < 1$, where the last equality is the Jacobi triple product identity. Three special cases of $f(a, b)$ are given by

$$\varphi(q) := f(q, q) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} q^{n^2} = \frac{(q^2; q^2)_\infty^5}{(q; q)_\infty^2 (q^4; q^4)_\infty^2},$$

$$\psi(q) := f(q, q^3) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} q^{n(n+1)/2} = \frac{(q^2; q^2)_\infty^2}{(q; q)_\infty},$$

$$f(-q) := f(-q, -q^2) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} (-1)^n q^{n(3n-1)/2} = (q; q)_\infty.$$

For $|z| < 1$, we also recall the Gaussian hypergeometric function ${}_2F_1$ given by

$${}_2F_1(a, b, c; z) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(a)_n (b)_n}{(c)_n} \frac{z^n}{n!},$$

where $(a)_n := a(a+1) \cdots (a+n-1)$ for $n \geq 1$ and $(a)_0 = 1$. Following Ramanujan [7], we define a modular equation of degree $n \in \mathbb{N}$ by a relation involving α and β such that

$$n \frac{{}_2F_1(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}, 1; 1-\alpha)}{{}_2F_1(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}, 1; \alpha)} = \frac{{}_2F_1(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}, 1; 1-\beta)}{{}_2F_1(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}, 1; \beta)},$$

in this case, we say that β has degree n over α . In his second notebook [7, pp. 236–237, Entry 13(i), (ii)], Ramanujan recorded the following modular equations of degree five without proof:

$$(\alpha\beta)^{1/2} + \{(1-\alpha)(1-\beta)\}^{1/2} + 2\{16\alpha\beta(1-\alpha)(1-\beta)\}^{1/6} = 1, \tag{1}$$

$$\left(\frac{\alpha^5}{\beta}\right)^{1/8} - \left(\frac{(1-\alpha)^5}{1-\beta}\right)^{1/8} = 1 + 2^{1/3} \left(\frac{\alpha^5(1-\alpha)^5}{\beta(1-\beta)}\right)^{1/24}. \tag{2}$$

In the third volume of his remarkable edition on Ramanujan’s notebooks, Berndt [2] proved (1) and (2) by employing the method of parametrization. Applying the transformation formulas found in [2, pp. 122–124, Entry 10, Entry 11, Entry 12], Berndt showed that these modular equations are equivalent to the following respective theta function identities.

Theorem 1. *We have the identities*

$$\frac{\varphi^5(q)}{\varphi(q^5)} + \frac{\varphi^5(-q^2)}{\varphi(-q^{10})} + 2\frac{f^5(q)}{f(q^5)} = 4\frac{\psi^5(q)}{\psi(q^5)}, \tag{3}$$

$$\varphi^2(q)\varphi^2(q^5) - \varphi^2(-q)\varphi^2(-q^5) - 16q^3\psi^2(q^2)\psi^2(q^{10}) = 8qf^2(-q^2)f^2(-q^{10}). \tag{4}$$

Berndt [2, p. 285] remarked that no direct proofs of (3) and (4) have been constructed. Baruah, Bora, and Ojah [1] proved Equation (4) using certain theta function identities.

In this note, we present a new proof of Theorem 1 by applying certain identities involving the Ramanujan’s function $k(q) := r(q)r^2(q^2)$ due to Cooper [4] and Chern and Tang [3], where $r(q)$ is the Rogers–Ramanujan continued fraction

$$r(q) := \frac{q^{1/5}}{1 + \frac{q}{1 + \frac{q^2}{1 + \frac{q^3}{1 + \dots}}}} = q^{1/5} \frac{(q, q^4; q^5)_{\infty}}{(q^2, q^3; q^5)_{\infty}}.$$

We then see that $k(q)$ has the infinite product representation given by

$$k(q) = q \frac{(q, q^2, q^8, q^9; q^{10})_\infty}{(q^3, q^4, q^6, q^7; q^{10})_\infty}.$$

The function $k(q)$ first appears in the second notebook [7, p. 326] of Ramanujan, who recorded the identities

$$r^5(q) = k(q) \left(\frac{1 - k(q)}{1 + k(q)} \right)^2, \quad r^5(q^2) = k^2(q) \left(\frac{1 + k(q)}{1 - k(q)} \right).$$

In his lost notebook [8, p. 56], Ramanujan also recorded the identities

$$r(q^{1/2}) = \frac{k^{1/10}(q)(1 + k(q))^{4/5}(1 - k(q))^{1/5}}{\sqrt{k(q) + \sqrt{1 + k(q) - k^2(q)}}},$$

$$r(q^4) = \left(\frac{1 - k(q)}{1 + k(q)} \right)^{1/10} \frac{2k^{4/5}(q)}{\sqrt{1 - k^2(q) + \sqrt{1 - 4k(q) - k^2(q)}}},$$

which were established by Kang [5] using theta function identities. We refer the reader to [4, 5, 9] for a list of identities involving $k(q)$. We remark that the aforementioned proof relies on a certain polynomial relation between $k(q)$ and $k(q^2)$ (see Theorem 4).

2. A New Proof of Theorem 1

We provide a new proof of Theorem 1 in this section. We start with listing the following important identities involving $k(q)$ found by Cooper [4, Theorem 3.5] and Chern and Tang [3, Theorem 3.3].

Lemma 2. *We have the identities*

$$\frac{f(-q^2)f^5(-q^5)}{qf(-q)f^5(-q^{10})} = \frac{1}{k(q)} - k(q), \tag{5}$$

$$\frac{f^4(-q^2)f^2(-q^5)}{qf^2(-q)f^4(-q^{10})} = \frac{1}{k(q)} + 1 - k(q), \tag{6}$$

$$\frac{f(-q)^3f(-q^5)}{qf(-q^2)f^3(-q^{10})} = \frac{1}{k(q)} - 4 - k(q). \tag{7}$$

Lemma 3. *We have the identity*

$$\frac{k(q)}{k(q^2)} - \frac{k(q^2)}{k(q)} = \frac{f(-q)f^3(-q^5)}{qf^4(-q^{10})}.$$

A consequence of Lemma 3 is the following polynomial relation between $k(q)$ and $k(q^2)$, which will play a key role in the proof of Theorem 1. We remark that Lee and Park [6] recently obtained this relation using the theory of modular functions.

Theorem 4. *We have the identity*

$$X^2 - Y + 2XY + X^2Y + Y^2 = 0,$$

where $X := k(q)$ and $Y := k(q^2)$.

Proof. We square the identity in Lemma 3 and use (5) and (7), so that

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{X}{Y} - \frac{Y}{X}\right)^2 &= \frac{f^2(-q)f^6(-q^5)}{q^2f^8(-q^{10})} = \frac{f(-q^2)f^5(-q^5)}{qf(-q)f^5(-q^{10})} \cdot \frac{f(-q)^3f(-q^5)}{qf(-q^2)f^3(-q^{10})} \\ &= \left(\frac{1}{X} - X\right) \left(\frac{1}{X} - 4 - X\right). \end{aligned}$$

Expanding the above equation leads to

$$\frac{(X^2 + Y - 2XY - X^2Y + Y^2)(X^2 - Y + 2XY + X^2Y + Y^2)}{X^2Y^2} = 0. \tag{8}$$

Using the q -expansion

$$k(q) = q - q^2 - q^3 + 2q^4 - 2q^6 + 2q^7 + O(q^8)$$

of $k(q)$, we note that the second factor of the numerator of Equation (8) vanishes while the first factor does not. Hence, the desired identity follows. \square

We are now ready to prove Theorem 1.

Proof of Theorem 1. We begin with proving Equation (3). Replacing q with $-q$ and noting that $\psi(-q) = f(-q)f(-q^4)/f(-q^2)$ and $\varphi(-q) = f^2(-q)/f(-q^2)$, we rewrite Equation (3) in terms of $f(-q)$ and multiply both sides by $f(-q^5)/f^5(-q)$ so that

$$\frac{f^5(-q)f(-q^{10})}{f^5(-q^2)f(-q^5)} + \frac{f^{10}(-q^2)f(-q^5)f(-q^{20})}{f^5(-q)f^5(-q^4)f^2(-q^{10})} + 2 = 4 \frac{f^5(-q^4)f(-q^{10})}{f^5(-q^2)f(-q^{20})}. \tag{9}$$

From Lemma 2, we have

$$\begin{aligned} A &:= \frac{f^5(-q)f(-q^{10})}{f^5(-q^2)f(-q^5)} = \frac{1 - 4X - X^2}{1 + X - X^2}, \\ B &:= \frac{f^5(-q^2)f(-q^{20})}{f^5(-q^4)f(-q^{10})} = \frac{1 - 4Y - Y^2}{1 + Y - Y^2}, \end{aligned}$$

where $X := k(q)$ and $Y := k(q^2)$. Then

$$\frac{5}{1-A} = \frac{1}{X} - X + 1, \tag{10}$$

$$C := \frac{5}{1-B} = \frac{1}{Y} - Y + 1. \tag{11}$$

In view of Theorem 4 and Equation (11), we deduce that

$$1 - 2X - X^2 = \frac{X^2}{Y} + Y = X^2(C + Y - 1) + Y = X^2(C - 1) + Y(X^2 + 1),$$

and solving this equation for Y , we get

$$Y = \frac{1 - 2X - X^2C}{X^2 + 1}. \tag{12}$$

Substituting Equation (12) into Theorem 4 and clearing denominators, we obtain

$$X^2C^2 - (1 - 2X + 2X^3 + X^4)C + (1 + X - X^2)^2 = 0,$$

or, in view of Equation (10),

$$C^2 - \left(\frac{1}{X^2} - \frac{2}{X} + 2X + X^2\right)C + \frac{25}{(1-A)^2} = 0. \tag{13}$$

Observe from Equation (10) that

$$\frac{1}{X^2} - \frac{2}{X} + 2X + X^2 = \left(\frac{1}{X} - X\right)^2 - 2\left(\frac{1}{X} - X\right) + 2 = \frac{5(A^2 + 2A + 2)}{(1-A)^2}. \tag{14}$$

Thus, combining (11), (13), and (14), we obtain

$$\frac{25}{(1-B)^2} - \frac{5(A^2 + 2A + 2)}{(1-A)^2} \cdot \frac{5}{1-B} + \frac{25}{(1-A)^2} = 0,$$

which, after clearing denominators, simplifies to

$$B^2 + A^2B + 2AB - 4A = 0. \tag{15}$$

Thus, we infer from Equation (15) that

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{f^5(-q)f(-q^{10})}{f^5(-q^2)f(-q^5)} + \frac{f^{10}(-q^2)f(-q^5)f(-q^{20})}{f^5(-q)f^5(-q^4)f^2(-q^{10})} + 2 &= A + \frac{B}{A} + 2 = \frac{A^2 + 2A + B}{A} \\ &= \frac{4}{B} = 4 \frac{f^5(-q^4)f(-q^{10})}{f^5(-q^2)f(-q^{20})}, \end{aligned}$$

which is exactly Equation (9). This completes the proof of Equation (3).

We next establish Equation (4). We rewrite this in terms of $f(-q)$ and divide both sides by $qf^2(-q^2)f^2(-q^{10})$ so that

$$\frac{f^8(-q^2)f^8(-q^{10})}{qf^4(-q)f^4(-q^4)f^4(-q^5)f^4(-q^{20})} - \frac{f^4(-q)f^4(-q^5)}{qf^4(-q^2)f^4(-q^{10})} - 16q^2 \frac{f^4(-q^4)f^4(-q^{20})}{f^4(-q^2)f^4(-q^{10})} = 8. \tag{16}$$

Using Lemma 2, we set

$$P := \frac{f^4(-q)f^4(-q^5)}{qf^4(-q^2)f^4(-q^{10})} = \left(\frac{1}{X} - 4 - X\right) \frac{1 - X^2}{1 + X - X^2},$$

$$Q := \frac{f^4(-q^2)f^4(-q^{10})}{q^2f^4(-q^4)f^4(-q^{20})} = \left(\frac{1}{Y} - 4 - Y\right) \frac{1 - Y^2}{1 + Y - Y^2}.$$

We see from the definitions of A and B that

$$P = \frac{A(A + 4)}{1 - A}, \tag{17}$$

$$Q = \frac{B(B + 4)}{1 - B}. \tag{18}$$

We rewrite Equation (17) as

$$P \left(\frac{1}{A} - 1\right) = A + 4.$$

Multiplying both sides of the above equation by B and invoking Equation (15), we infer that

$$AB + 4B = P \left(\frac{B}{A} - B\right) = P \left(\frac{4}{B} - A - B - 2\right),$$

which yields

$$A = \frac{4P - 2BP - B^2(P + 4)}{B(B + P)}. \tag{19}$$

Plugging in Equation (19) into Equation (15) and clearing denominators, we deduce that

$$B(B + 4)(B - 1)P^2 + 8(B - 1)(B^2 + 2B + 2)P + B^2(B + 4)^2 = 0. \tag{20}$$

We note from Equation (18) that

$$\frac{B^2 + 2B + 2}{1 - B} = \frac{B^2 + 4B}{1 - B} + 2 = Q + 2. \tag{21}$$

Thus, dividing both sides of Equation (20) by $(1 - B)^2$ and applying (18) and (21), we arrive at

$$-P^2Q - 8PQ - 16P + Q^2 = 0,$$

which implies that

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{f^8(-q^2)f^8(-q^{10})}{qf^4(-q)f^4(-q^4)f^4(-q^5)f^4(-q^{20})} - \frac{f^4(-q)f^4(-q^5)}{qf^4(-q^2)f^4(-q^{10})} - 16q^2 \frac{f^4(-q^4)f^4(-q^{20})}{f^4(-q^2)f^4(-q^{10})} \\ &= \frac{Q}{P} - P - \frac{16}{Q} = \frac{Q^2 - P^2Q - 16P}{PQ} = 8 \end{aligned}$$

as desired. This completes the proofs of (16) and (4). \square

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